

H63D Syndrome Research Consortium

www.h63d.org

International H63D Mutation Research Consortium

A non-profit science association. Founded in 2000.

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Open Academic Letter to the Global Medical Community

Oshtoran Syndrome, PANS-H63D-Multisystemic Instability Syndrome, and H63D-Syndrome Type-3: Clarification and Unification of Nomenclature

From the Desk of Riku Honda, Chairman of the H63D Mutation Syndrome Research Consortium

Dear Esteemed Colleagues,

It is with great urgency and academic rigor that I address you today as the Chairman of the H63D Mutation Syndrome Research Consortium. The matter at hand concerns the scientific nomenclature and ongoing research of a medical condition known variously as Oshtoran Syndrome, PANS-H63D-Multisystemic Instability Syndrome, and H63D-Syndrome Type-3.

The syndrome first came to light in 2016, identified by Dr. Madjid Zafarian, his brother Dr. Hamed Zafarian and colleagues. Although the study had substantial merit in terms of its discovery, it regrettably did not adhere to the globally accepted norms of scientific publishing. Simultaneously, the name "Oshtoran Syndrome" was appropriated by the Marvel Entertainment franchise, a turn of events that risked delegitimizing the condition in the academic community.

Fast forward to Spring 2023, an independent research group led by Jacob Adams discovered a syndrome strikingly similar to that described by Dr. Zafarian, his brother and colleagues. After establishing direct contact facilitated by prior student research, it became clear that both groups had identified the same condition.

Two significant issues emerged: the inadequacy of Dr. Zafarian's initial publication and the lack of interest from Adams's group in furthering the research. It was at this juncture that we, the H63D Consortium, were invited to take over the scientific custodianship of the syndrome. Given our extensive network of over 200 volunteer non-profit clinicians and biologists, who contribute to our consortium's research initiatives outside of their regular clinical duties, we were uniquely positioned for this role.

Dr. Zafarian graciously agreed to cede future research to our consortium and the terms were outlined that the syndrome could also be referred to as H63D Syndrome Type-3. This was particularly pragmatic given the unforeseeable manner in which the Marvel franchise might manipulate the name "Oshtoran Syndrome."

It should be underscored that the consortium's comprehensive studies can typically span 3 to 8 years. However, in light of the exigency, we encourage the global medical community to consider the recent, albeit preliminary, paper by Adams et al. (2023) as a guiding resource in the interim. We believe that despite its initial methodological shortcomings, the syndrome as identified should be taken seriously, as it is not only treatable but also appears to be more prevalent than previously assumed.

In conclusion, while the initial work by Dr. Zafarian and the accelerated findings by Adams et al. may not fully meet the rigorous standards one typically expects, their contributions are nonetheless invaluable. Ignoring this condition on account of its complex publication history would be, from a medical ethics standpoint, indefensible.

For questions from the scientific community and practicing physicians, we are available for general information at **team@h63d.org**.

Private individuals may contact us via the contact form on **www.h63d.org**

Sincerely,
Riku Honda, M.Sc.
Chairman

Further information:

Zafarian, Hamed (2016)

https://issuu.com/oshtoran.syndrome/docs/oshtoran_syndrome_case_report_iix

Zafarian, Madjid et al. (2016)

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Pascal Wagner (2016) Oshtoran Syndrome. SCRIBD ePub

Davis, Benjamin, Levi, Daniel M., Gupta, Rahul, Zahedi, Hamed, Shirazi, Mohammad, & Smith, Samantha N. (2022). Oshtoran Syndrome meets Spider-Man: How a group of Iranian amateur researchers inadvertently influenced pop culture. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7109840>

Adams, Jacob, Nathan, Simon, Feldman, Jo, Honda, Riku, Asgari, Ali, Ivanova, Olga, & Diamandis, Carolina. (2023). Management and multi-disciplinary approach in complex cases of PANS-H63D-Multisystemic Instability Syndrome. In Zenodo OpenAire: Vol. July 2023 (7.1, Number ePub). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8299513>

Zafarian, Madjid. (2023). Congratulations for having discovered Oshtoran Syndrome a second time. In OpenAire: Vol. ePub (Number Sep 2023). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8320541>

H63D, Research Consortium. (2023). The Imperative of Publishing Data on Rare Diseases like PANS-H63D-Multisystemic Instability Syndrome. Openaire, 09/23(ePub). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8311693>

Feldman, Jo, Honda, Riku, Schneider, Katharina, Schmidt, Richard, & Tudor, Adrian. (2023). Oshtoran Syndrome aka Spider-Man's Disease or PANS-H63D-Instability-Syndrome: A rare illness amplified by pop culture and scientific perseverance. In Zenodo openAir: Vol. September 2023. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8322986>